

Mixed ligand polymeric complexes of iron-, cobalt-, nickel-, palladium- and platinum(II) with 1,4-dithiopurazine. Part-II

P. D. Singh^a, Gunjan Kumari^a, Kumud Kumari^a, Ratan K. Choudhary^b and L. K. Mishra^{a*}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Patna University, Patna-800 005, India

^bM. K. College, Laheriasarai, Darbhanga-846 003, India

Manuscript received 18 July 1996, revised 5 February 1999, accepted 16 February 1999

Polymeric complexes of bivalent metal ions with 1,4-dithiopurazine (dtpuH₂) of general formula, M(dtpu)Py₃.nH₂O (*n* = 0 for M = Co^{II} and 2 for M = Fe^{II} or Ni^{II}), M(dtpu)Py₂ (M = Pd^{II} or Pt^{II}) and M(dtpu)Py_{3-n}(H₂O)_n (*n* = 1 for Ni^{II} and 2 for Co^{II}) have been prepared.

In a previous communication¹, we reported polymeric complexes of some bivalent metal ions with 1,4-dithiopurazine (dtpuH₂). The ligand coordinates as dianionic quadridentate bridging chelating molecule in solution forming insoluble ML₂.nH₂O with bivalent metal ions. In the present communication, we report polymeric pyridino adducts of bivalent Co, Ni, Fe, Pd and Pt with 1,4-dithiopurazine (dtpuH₂).

Results and Discussion

The ligand (dtpuH₂) formed stable, insoluble pyridine adducts of composition, M(dtpu)Py₃.2H₂O (M = Ni^{II}, Fe^{II}); Co(dtpu)Py₃; M(dtpu)Py₂ (M = Pd^{II}, Pt^{II}); Co(dtpu)Py₂.2H₂O and Ni(dtpu)Py₂.H₂O (Table 1). The complexes were found slightly soluble in DMF and DMSO and their DMF solutions showed negligible conductance (3–5 Ω⁻¹ mol⁻¹ cm²) indicating their non-ionic character. The insolubility of the complexes in common organic solvents indicates their polymeric nature. The complexes Ni(dtpu)Py₃.2H₂O and Fe(dtpu)Py₃.2H₂O partially lose water and pyridine molecules each below 120° yielding M(dtpu)Py₂.H₂O (M = Ni^{II}, Fe^{II}); but Co(dtpu)Py₂.2H₂O, Ni(dtpu)Py₂.H₂O and Co(dtpu)Py₃ are stable below 120° indicating that retained pyridine and water molecules are bonded strongly in the Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Fe^{II} complexes whereas one pyridine and one water molecule each are either hydrogen bonded or loosely held up in crystal lattice of the former Ni^{II} and Fe^{II} complexes.

The complexes of Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} are diamagnetic suggesting their square-planar structure. The Ni^{II}, Co^{II} and Fe^{II} complexes are paramagnetic. The magnetic moment values of Ni(dtpu)Py₃.2H₂O (3.38 B.M.) and Ni(dtpu)Py₂.H₂O (3.10 B.M.) occur in the range of high-spin octahedral or five-coordinated trigonal-bipyramidal structure². The magnetic moments of Co(dtpu)Py₃ (4.47 B.M.) and Co(dtpu)Py₂.2H₂O (4.16 B.M.) indicate their pseudo-tetrahedral or five-coordinated trigonal-bipyramidal structure³. The magnetic moment of Fe(dtpu)Py₃.2H₂O (4.49 B.M.) suggests

five- or six-coordinated structure. The low magnetic moment values for the Co^{II} and Fe^{II} complexes can be attributed to spin-state equilibrium at room temperature⁴. Due to lack of facility to measure magnetic susceptibility at low temperature, the spin-state equilibrium could not be substantiated.

Table 1. Analytical data of complex*

Compd	Colour	Metal (%)	
		Found	(Calcd)
Co(dtpu)Py ₃	Red	13 63	(13 33)
Co(dtpu)Py ₂ .2H ₂ O	Red	22 18	(21 88)
Ni(dtpu)Py ₃ .2H ₂ O	Green	12 68	(12 29)
Ni(dtpu)Py ₂ .H ₂ O	Yellow	15 68	(15 41)
Fe(dtpu)Py ₃ .2H ₂ O	Green	11 80	(11 76)
Pd(dtpu)Py ₂	Red	26 30	(25 92)
Pt(dtpu)Py ₂	Yellow	39 39	(39 09)

*All compounds gave satisfactory N analysis

The electronic absorption spectrum of ligand in ethanol reveals a strong band at 33560 (ε_{max} = 20400) and a shoulder at 29410 cm⁻¹ attributable to π-π* and n-π* transitions. The reflectance spectra of Ni(dtpu)Py₃.2H₂O and Ni(dtpu)Py₂.H₂O display four bands at 10460 and 10200; 14390 and 14080; 17390 and 15530; 25530 and 24390 cm⁻¹ respectively, assignable to transitions from ground state ³E' → ³A''₁, ³A''₂ (F); ³E' → ³A'₂ (F); ³E' → ³E'' (P) and ³E' → ³A'₂ (P), similar to five-coordinated nickel(II) complexes^{5,6}. The low intensity of the bands precludes the possibility of tetrahedral structure. The possibility of coordination number six cannot be ruled out but the stoichiometry of stable product supports coordination number five for the complexes. The solid reflectance spectra of Co(dtpu)Py₃ and Co(dtpu)Py.(H₂O)₂ show bands at 13790 and 13510; 15240 and 16540; 18660 and 20750 cm⁻¹ assignable to ⁴A''₂ → ⁴E' (F) → ⁴A'₂ (P) and → ⁴E'' (P) transitions, similar to a number of five-coordinated cobalt(II) complexes⁵. The occurrence of reflectance band at low energy (13500 cm⁻¹) and magnetic moment value of 4.16–

4.47 B.M. at room temperature preclude the possibility of high-spin octahedral coordination. The low intensity of reflectance bands and stoichiometry of the complexes reduce the probability of tetrahedral geometry. Therefore, five-coordinated ligand bridged structure is suggested for both the Ni^{II} and Co^{II} complexes^{5,6}. A band at 20000 cm⁻¹ of Pd(dtpu)Py₂ is assigned to ¹A_{1g} → ¹A_{2g} transition in planar field. The other transitions expected for planar complexes in higher energy are probably enveloped under C-T transition.

The ir spectra of the ligand display NH stretches at 3162 and 3058 cm⁻¹. The aquopyridino complexes show a broad band at 3150–3300 cm⁻¹ attributed from ν_{N-H} coupled with ν_{OH} of H₂O vibration. The ligand dtpuH₂ does not contain –CH₂– or C–H group, therefore a medium band of 2820 cm⁻¹ is unambiguously assigned to thiol ν_{SH}. In the complexes, the ν_{SH} vibration disappears indicating that deprotonated thiol-sulphur is bonded to the metal atom. The thioamide band I (1540, 1480 cm⁻¹ s.br)⁷ of the ligand is shifted to higher frequency on coordination and observed at 1550–1575 cm⁻¹. In pyridino complexes a strong and sharp band observed at 1590–1610 cm⁻¹ is attributed to ν_{C=N} of coordinated pyridine⁸. In aquopyridino species the ν_{C=N} is broad due to some contribution of δ_{H₂O}. The thioamide band II (1380) and III (1040 cm⁻¹) are also shifted in the complexes at higher frequencies by 15–20 cm⁻¹. The thioamide band IV (707 cm⁻¹) due to ν_{C=S} is shifted to lower frequency and couples with pyridine ring vibration at 690–695 cm⁻¹ and observed as a strong band. The red-shift of thioamide band IV supports the bonding of deprotonated thiol-sulphur to metal atom^{9,10}. All the complexes display pyridine ring breathing mode of vibration at 1010 the 1040 cm⁻¹ due to coordinated pyridine¹⁰. The pyridine molecule (C–H) out-of-plane bending is observed at 755 ± 2 cm⁻¹. The new sharp ir bands at 625, 585 and 530 cm⁻¹ observed in the pyridino complexes are characteristic vibrations of coordinated pyridine⁸. The aquo complexes display a broad band at 635 ± 5 cm⁻¹ attributed to δ_{H₂O} of coordinated water¹¹. In far-ir region, the ligand displays a broad band at 500–450 and strong bands at 425 and 298 cm⁻¹, which precludes the assignment of ν_{(M-N)/(M-S)} in complexes.

Experimental

The ligand 1,4-dithiopurazine (dtpuH₂) was prepared by the reported method¹². A mixture of thiohydrazide (1 mmol) in hot water (100 ml) and trithiodiglycollic acid (1 mmol) dissolved in aqueous 1 N NaOH solution (200 ml)

was refluxed on a water-bath for 2 h when cream coloured dtpuH₂ separated on cooling, m.p. 176°.

M(dtpu)Py₃.nH₂O (*n* = 0) for *M* = Co^{II}, 2 for Ni^{II} or Fe^{II}) and *M(dtpu)Py₂* (*M* = Pd^{II} or Pt^{II}) :

An aqueous ethanolic solution (50 ml) of the metal chloride (0.01 mol) containing pyridine (5 ml) was refluxed with the ligand dissolved in hot pyridine (0.01 mol in 30 ml). The pyridino complexes either separated immediately or by refluxing it on a steam-bath for 0.5 h. The product was filtered, washed with ethanol containing a few drops of pyridine and dried in a desiccator over KOH. In case of Pd^{II} or Pt^{II} the metal chloride was dissolved in aqueous ethanol; iron(II) complex was prepared under nitrogen atmosphere (yields 80–95%).

Co(dtpu)Py.(H₂O)₂ and *Ni(dtpu)py₂.H₂O* : Co(dtpu)Py₃ and Ni(dtpu)Py₃.2H₂O in aqueous ethanol was refluxed for 1 h on a steam-bath. The product was washed with ethanol and dried as above. Reflectance spectra and magnetic susceptibility were determined as reported earlier¹³. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer.

References

1. P. D. Singh and L. K. Mishra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **58**, 333.
2. L. Sacconi, P. Nannelli, N. Nardi and U. Campigli, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 943; A. B. P. Lever, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 763.
3. M. Ciampolini and N. Nardi, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, **5**, 41; U. N. Tripathi, G. Srivastava and R. C. Mehrotra, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1994, **509**, 564; M. C. R. M. P. Basto and A. A. S. C. Machado, *Synth. React. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1995, **25**, 1101.
4. R. J. Dossier, W. J. Eilbeck, A. E. Underhill, P. R. Edwards and C. E. Johnson, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1969, 810; E. König and K. Madeja, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **88**, 4528; R. N. Sylva and H. A. Godwin, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1967, **20**, 479; 1968, **21**, 83.
5. M. Ciampolini and N. Nardi, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1967, **6**, 446.
6. M. Ciampolini, N. Nardi and G. P. Speroni, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1966, **1**, 222.
7. C. N. R. Rao and R. Venkataraghavan, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1962, **18**, 541; C. N. R. Rao, R. Venkataraghavan and T. R. Kasturi, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1964, **42**, 36.
8. N. S. Gill, R. H. Nuttall, D. E. Scaife and D. W. A. Sharp, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1961, **18**, 79.
9. R. D. Bereman, D. M. Baird, J. Bordner and J. Dorfmar, *Polyhedron*, 1983, **2**, 25.
10. M. K. Das, M. Nath and J. J. Zuckerman, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1983, **21**, 49.
11. K. Nakamoto, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Wiley, New York, 1978.
12. J. Sandström, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1961, **15**, 1575.
13. S. P. Ghosh and L. K. Mishra, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1973, **7**, 545; R. R. Prasad, L. K. Mishra, Ratan K. Choudhary, C. M. Jha and J. K. Jha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1998, **75**, 499.